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CONCORDANCE OF INSCRIPTIONS AT AL ḤANĀKĪYA (جبل العهين)

Jabal al-Ḥayn (جبل العهين sometimes Jabal Uhayn, Uhain or Uhain mount) is a prominent outcrop of red sandstone in Saudi Arabia, known for its pre-historic petroglyphs, tribal markings (*wusūm*) and inscriptions in early Semitic languages as well as Arabic. The mountain is located in Medina Province, about 17.5 km north-east of the town of al-Ḥanākīyā (الحناكية) at 24°59'21"N 40°38'27"E.

جبل العهين الحناكية. Aerial view of the mountain, courtesy of wikimedia commons.

Introduction. Among the petroglyphs and inscriptions at Jabal al-Ḥayn are a number in Arabic which date to the early years of the Islamic calendar. One inscription quotes Qur'ān 18:21. The inscription was first studied and published by F. M. Donner (1984). Following a frequently found formula, the inscription implores God to grant forgiveness and then bears witness to the hour of judgement. For a digital version of the original photograph see Willis (2021). In a second record of singular historical importance, an individual named Rāfi' bin 'Alī declares "I believe that there is no God except Him in whom the children of Israel believed, (believing as) a Muslim Hanif; nor am I among the polytheists." (Donner, 1984). Also published by Donner is an inscription on a boulder invoking the name of God and giving an exceptional religious maxim. For a digital version of the original photograph see Willis (2021).

These and the other inscriptions from the site are listed in *Thesaurus d'épigraphie islamique*, an online research resource supported by the Max van Berchem Foundation, founded in 1973 in honour of the celebrated epigraphist Max von Berchem (1863-1921).

Concordance. The purpose of this concordance is to provide a guide to one cluster of inscriptions at Jabal al-Ḥayn that dates to the earliest Islamic centuries. The list provides the FICHE number of *Thesaurus d'épigraphie islamique* with the corresponding number assigned by F. M. Donner. Below is a photograph of this cluster with the drawing prepared by Donner. Inscription W8 (FICHE 14562) awaits full study and publication; only [... بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم (الرحيم)] has been read to date.

[FICHE 14560](#) [= Donner W6]

[FICHE 14561](#) [= Donner W7]

[FICHE 14563](#) [= Donner W9]

[FICHE 14564](#) [= Donner W10]

[FICHE 14565](#) [= Donner W11]

[FICHE 14566](#) [= Donner W12]

Bibliography

Donner, F. M. (1984). Some Early Arabic Inscriptions from Al-Ḥanākīyya, Saudi Arabia. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4575259>

Willis, M. (2021). الحناكية al-Ḥanākīyā. جبل العهين Arabic inscriptions on a rock face with prayers for forgiveness. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4676253>

Willis, M. (2021). الحناكية al-Hanākīyā. جبل العهين Arabic inscription quoting Qur'ān 18: 21. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4630352>

Willis, M. (2021). الحناكية al-Hanākīyā. جبل العهين Arabic inscription giving a religious maxim. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4633074>

W 6 بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
وحمدا لله على

W 7 بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
الحناكية
بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
الحناكية

W 8 بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
الحناكية

W 9 بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
الحناكية

W 10 بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
الحناكية

W 11 اللهم اعقد
لمرئيتك هذا
الخط

W 12 بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
الحناكية